

Triterpenoids. XXXIX. The Constitution of Barrinic Acid- A New Triterpene Acid from *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn

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Received 14 January 1972

The isolation of a new triterpene acid called Acid-A from the branch wood of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn was reported in our preliminary communication¹ and it was shown to be 2,3,19-trihydroxyolean-12-ene-23 (or 24), 28-dioic acid. Further studies on the constitution of this acid, now called barrinic acid (Ia), is reported here.

Dimethyl barrinate (Ib) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the product was directly acetylated by heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride on steam bath when a tetra-acetate $C_{38}H_{58}O_9$, m.p. 120°–23° was obtained. Its mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at m/e 658 and a peak at m/e 292 due to the ion species (a). Dehydration of the above tetra-acetate with $POCl_3$ in pyridine furnished a product which showed u.v. absorption maxima at 243, 251 and 261 m μ typical of $\Delta^{11:12}$, $^{13:18}$ -dienes of the oleanane series. This diene on mild saponification furnished a compound, $C_{30}H_{48}O_4$, m.p. 280°–83°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} -93^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$); (M^+ 472). Its u.v. spectrum showed absorption maxima at 244 (log ϵ 4.25), 251 (log ϵ 4.26) and 260 (log ϵ 4.09) m μ . The chemical and physical properties of this product is very similar to those reported for compound (II) by Row *et al.*² and therefore the two compounds should be identical.

On the basis of the above observation and those reported in our preliminary communication¹, the structure of barrinic acid may be represented as 2 α , 3 β , 19 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-en-23, 28-dioic acid (Ia).

The N.M.R. spectrum of diacetyl dimethyl barrinate (Ic) has also been found to be in good agreement with the proposed structure. The four sharp singlets in the high field region at 0.69 (3H), 0.91 (3H), 0.99 (6H) and 1.28 δ (6H) were due to the six quaternary methyl groups ($-C-CH_3$). High field shift of one of the methyl groups to 0.69 δ showed the presence of a 28-carbomethoxyl group³. The 28-carbomethoxyl group appeared as a sharp singlet at the expected³ region 3.63 δ (3H; $-COOCH_3$). The presence of the 23-carbomethoxyl group caused the downshift of 24-methyl group⁴ to 1.28 δ . The signal for the 23-carbomethoxyl group was observed at 3.71 δ (3H; $-COOCH_3$; S). The vicinal acetoxy groups at C-2 and C-3 appeared as twin peaks at 2.0 (3H; $-OCOCH_3$; S) and 2.09 δ (3H; $-OCOCH_3$; S). The C-2 β (axial) proton appeared as a multiplet centred at 5.57 δ (1H; $H-C-O-COCH_3$) and the corresponding C-3 axial (α) proton appeared as a doublet at 4.85 δ (1H; $H-C-O-COCH_3$;

$J = 10$ c.p.s.)³. The large coupling constant ($J = 10$ c.p.s.)³ indicated the *trans* diaxial relationship⁵ of the above two protons which necessitates *trans* diequatorial relationship between the two acetoxy groups (i.e., 2α , 3β) as shown in (Ia). The C-12 vinyl proton gave rise to a broad multiplet centred at 5.43δ which was partly overlapped by the signal for the C-2 axial (β) proton. The signal for the C-19 β proton ($HC-OH$) appeared at 3.35δ (1H, m) and the signal at 1.7δ (1; $H-C-OH$) was attributed to the proton of the free hydroxyl group as it disappeared on D_2O exchange.

I

II

- a, $R_1=R_2=H$
 b, $R_1=H; R_2=CH_3$
 c, $R_1=COCH_3; R_2=CH_3$

a

 m/e 292

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. M. Sircar, Director and Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, for their interest in this work. Thanks are due to Dr. B. C. Das, C.N.R.S., France and Dr. K. G. Das and Dr. A. P. B. Sinha of the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, India, for the mass and n.m.r. spectra.

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